

Decoding Combinations: A Review of Analytical Approaches for Dextromethorphan and Chlorpheniramine Maleate

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ABSTRACT

Chlorpheniramine maleate (CPM) and Dextromethorphan hydrobromide (DXM) are two common co-formulated agents in expectorant formulations, widely available as over-the-counter medications. For ensuring quality control and regulatory compliance, their simultaneous determination in various pharmaceutical dosage forms is critical. This review comprises an overview of the analytical techniques reported between 2010 and 2024 for the quantification of CPM and DXM, both as single agents and combination therapies. Techniques including UV spectrophotometry, HPLC, GC, TLC, hyphenated techniques (LC-MS/MS, UHPLC-MS/MS), and capillary electrophoresis are discussed, which helps in future studies and research involving these actives.

KEYWORDS: Chlorpheniramine maleate, Dextromethorphan hydrobromide, HPLC, GC, TLC, UV Spectrophotometry

INTRODUCTION

The method of drug discovery, development, and release in the market all depend on the advancement of analytical methods. From the formulation development stage to the commercial batch of product, the technique of development, optimization, and validation of the drug product is crucial. Since dextromethorphan hydrobromide (DXM) and chlorpheniramine maleate (CPM) are the most often used cough and cold medication combinations, it is crucial to develop and validate analytical methods for them⁽¹⁾.

Chlorpheniramine Maleate (CPM) is a first-generation alkylamine H1-antihistamine, chemically defined as *3-(4-chlorophenyl)-N,N-dimethyl-3-pyridin-2-yl-propan-1-amine*⁽²⁾. It exerts its pharmacological action by blocking H1 histamine receptors, thereby inhibiting the physiological effects mediated by histamine. Although primarily administered orally, CPM can also be given via intravenous (IV), intramuscular (IM), or subcutaneous (SC) routes. Due to its ability to cross the blood-brain barrier, CPM often causes mild sedation and anticholinergic side effects, which are particularly pronounced in elderly patients^(3,4).

Dextromethorphan, the synthetic opioid derivative and dextrorotatory isomer of levorphanol, has been marketed as an antitussive since its FDA approval in 1958. It inhibits cough reflexes by acting at the medullary cough center and binding at sigma opioid receptors in the

CNS, thereby elevating serotonin levels⁽⁵⁾. Unlike codeine, dextromethorphan causes relatively little central nervous system depression and has no analgesic effects. It undergoes significant CYP2D6 metabolism to produce its active metabolite, dextrorphan, which is glucuronidated to dextrorphan-o-glucuronide and has a low blood-brain barrier penetration rate⁽⁶⁾.

CYP3A4 also metabolizes it to 3- methoxymorphinan. It is also present in OTC combination with anti-histamines and decongestants, dextromethorphan serves as a vital component in treating cough by altering the brainstem's cough centre, the nucleus tractus solitaries⁽⁷⁾.

Figure 1: Structural formula of CPM (a) and DXM (b)

The aim of this review is to compile and evaluate all reported analytical methods developed for formulations containing both CPM and DXM. This includes techniques such as chromatography, electrophoresis, spectrophotometry, and other hyphenated techniques.

Clinical background

Chlorpheniramine maleate helps in the symptomatic treatment allergic diseases such as hay fever, urticaria, and allergic rhinitis by antagonizing histamine H₁ receptors. Interestingly, CPM typically produces less sedation than other first-generation antihistamines⁽²⁾. Recent research has examined CPM's potential for treating ailments like asthma, nasal congestion, rhinorrhoea & chronic urticaria in addition to its traditional uses, suggesting a wider therapeutic range⁽⁴⁾. A levorphanol derivative and codeine analogue, dextromethorphan hydrobromide is frequently used as a cough suppressant. It acts on CNS and relieves cough brought on by mild irritation of the throat and bronchi. These two drugs are usually found in the combined form and are available in various formulations. Marketed drug products reveal numerous combinations combining other compounds along with dextromethorphan and chlorpheniramine maleate⁽⁵⁻⁷⁾.

Data collection

This review is based on a careful study of the literature from the last decade (2010–2024). Various sources, such as international journals, books, and other scholarly publications, were utilized for this purpose. The topic was thoroughly explored through general academic databases like PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science. In addition to that, specialized Pharmaceutical and Chemical Databases like ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, and

American Chemical Society publications were carefully examined to get comprehensive coverage of the topic. Pharmacological information from Drug Bank was also carefully examined. Data collected reveals that CPM and DXM are mostly combined along with drugs such as Paracetamol(PA), Phenylephrine (PE), Dexchlorpheniramine maleate(DCPM), Dextrophan (DT), Betamethasone(BTM), Pseudoephedrine(PSE), Guaifenesin(GUF), Aspirin (AS), Caffeine anhydrous (CA), Levocetirizine(LCZ), Bromhexine(BRX), Ibuprofen(IBU), Levochlorpersaline fenodizoate (LCF), Dexamethasone(DEX), Tramadol(TRD), Diphenhydramine(DPH), and Ephedrine(EPD).

Analytical Profiles of Dextromethorphan and Chlorpheniramine in Combination Therapies

Several articles detail the various analytical techniques for estimating CPM and DXM alone as well as in combinations ^(8,9,12-49). The Indian Pharmacopoeia states that the method for determining DXM uses a silica gel column and a combination of buffer solution, tetrahydrofuran, methanol, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, and water as the stationary phase and mobile phase, respectively ⁽¹⁰⁾. The liquid chromatographic method for determining CPM uses an ODS column as the stationary phase and a mobile phase consisting of buffer solution and acetonitrile ⁽¹¹⁾. There are several spectroscopic, chromatographic, and electrophoretic techniques available for the simultaneous identification of the indicated medications in mixed formulations. However, liquid chromatographic techniques are used in the majority of development approaches.

UV Spectroscopic method

Khalod *et al.* (2012) developed a new, easy, sensitive, and precise spectrophotometric technique for the simultaneous measurement of chlorpheniramine maleate and dextromethorphan hydrobromide in a syrup formulation. This approach uses the derivative spectroscopic method to solve the problem. The absorbance maxima of dextromethorphan hydrobromide and chlorpheniramine maleate occurred at 262.6 nm and 289.2 nm, respectively, using methanol. Beer's Law was followed for both pharmaceuticals in the concentration range of 10–70 µg/ml, and the suggested method was validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, specificity, precision, and robustness. For both medications, the regression coefficient (r^2) was found to be 0.999 ⁽¹²⁾.

Masoud Shariati-Rad *et al.* (2013) identified PA, DXM, PE, and CPM in pharmaceutical formulations concurrently using partial least squares. The method was based on chemotherapeutic and UV spectrophotometry. They made use of the absorption data in the 220–300 nm range. Although the technique was verified and demonstrated strong linearity, accuracy, and precision, it was constrained by matrix interferences and spectral resolution overlap ⁽¹³⁾.

Mustarichie *et al.* (2014) studied the Dual-wavelength UV method, applying it to DCPM and BTM tablets. The method was developed using a phosphate buffer of pH 7.2 measuring at 239nm and 262nm. They achieved excellent linearity and accuracy. The LOD for DCPM was 2.261 ppm at 239 nm and 0.707 ppm at 262 nm, while for BTM, the LODs were 0.088

ppm at 239 nm and 0.127 ppm at 262 nm. The LOQ were 7.536 ppm and 2.357 ppm for DCPM, and 0.295 ppm and 0.425 ppm for BTM at the respective wavelengths⁽¹⁴⁾.

Vineeta V. Khanvilkar *et.al* (2016) proposed a simple UV spectrophotometric technique to measure DXM in bulk materials and commercially available dosage forms, particularly chewable tablets and lozenges. It involves the use of HCl (0.1 N) as solvent to determine the maximum absorbance of DXM at 278 nm. A linear calibration curve was formed in the range of 5.0 to 30.0 µg/mL and with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9993. Recovery studies, which yielded mean percentages of 100.66 and 101.37 for lozenges and 100.76 and 101.17 for chewable pills, illustrated the procedure's accuracy⁽¹⁵⁾.

Kirtimaya Mishra, *et al.* (2016) created and verified a UV-visible spectrophotometric technique to determine CPM in pharmaceutical tablets and its pure form. At 262 nm, the method determined the maximum absorbance of CPM using 0.1N hydrogen chloride as the solvent. Linearity was confirmed in the concentration range of 10 to 60 µg/mL. Correlation coefficient (R^2) was found to be 0.999. Recovery studies were used to evaluate accuracy; percentages ranging from 98.62% to 99.17% showed that excipient interference was low. The method's insensitivity to slight changes in analytical conditions confirmed its robustness. All other validation parameters also showed the results aligning to ICH guidelines⁽¹⁶⁾.

Maria Ashfaq, *et al* (2017) developed and validated a UV-spectrophotometric technique for the detection of CPM in controlled release tablet and bulk forms. Developed method utilizes acetate buffer (pH 4.5), phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), distilled water (pH 7.0), and 0.1N hydrochloric acid (HCl) buffer (pH 1.2) as the solvent systems with which the absorbance of CPM was evaluated. Of all the solvents tested, 0.1N HCl provided the most drug absorption, while CPM had the maximum absorbance at 261 nm. The method showed linearity between 20 and 60 µg/mL values, with an R^2 value of 0.9998. Accuracy or recovery studies were done at 3 different levels, and all individual recoveries were found to be over 99%. The LOD and LOQ were reported to be 2.2 µg/mL and 6.6 µg/mL, respectively. The efficacy of this approach in monitoring the quality of CPM in pharmaceuticals is demonstrated by each of the validation criteria given, which all meet ICH requirements⁽¹⁷⁾.

Rida Evalina Tarigan, *et.al* (2020) developed and validated a UV Spectrophotometry method with dual divisor ratio spectra derivative technique for the simultaneous measurement of DXM, DOX, PSE in tablet formulations. The described method utilized ethanol as the solvent and took measurements of absorbance at 277.0 nm for DEX, 243.0 nm for DOX, and 243.2 nm for PSE. This technique achieved separation of overlapping spectra which made it possible to measure the amount of each ingredient without interference caused by excipients. The method showed a remarkable degree of linearity. In recovery studies, mean percentages were found to be 100.88% for DEX, 100.05% for DOX, and 100.26% for PSE demonstrating accuracy. Reliability was also established with a reported RSD of less than 2%⁽¹⁸⁾.

Chromatographic methods

Drug identification and estimation in multicomponent pharmaceutical formulations is feasible with chromatographic techniques such as HPLC, GC, and TLC, all of which as well as some other absorbance methods are used in quality assurance and regulatory checks. Unlike other methods, these techniques have improved precision, sensitivity, and specificity. Spectroscopic techniques face a greater challenge when estimating several drugs at once because of overlapping spectra and matrix interferences, but are solvable through chromatographic methods giving effective separation and quantification of each component. Besides ensuring safety and accurate dosage, degradation products, impurities and stability of drugs can also be determined. Chromatographic methods are advanced and are essential to develop robust and valid testing of pharmaceuticals.

Thin layer chromatography

Manpreet Kaur Chahal *et al.* (2016) used a TLC analysis to detect the components of popular OTC antitussives. Finding and measuring the active ingredients in these formulations was the main goal of the investigation. DXM, CPM, and other typical excipients were among these substances. We looked at twenty solvent systems, and we discovered that solvent system A, which had methanol and ammonia in a ratio of 100 to 1.5 (v/v), and solvent system B, which had methanol and chloroform in a ratio of 90 to 10 (v/v), were the most appropriate since they effectively separated the various components of these preparations. Iodine fuming technique was used as the visualising technique for analysing the chromatograms ⁽¹⁹⁾.

Nehal F. Farid *et al.* (2017) created and verified a densitometric TLC technique for estimating drug formulations that incorporate DEX and CPM, along with methyl and propyl parabens as preservatives. Hexane, acetone, and ammonia (5.5:4.5:0.5 v/v/v) made up the mobile phase used in the silica gel TLC F254 plates used for the investigation. Researchers found that the technique has great sensitivity and selectivity at 254 nm. With mean recoveries of 99.12% and 100.14%, the linearity ranges for dexamethasone were 0.1–1.7 µg/band and the CPM ranged from 0.4–2.8 µg/band. This demonstrated an exceptional level of precision and RSD was within limit. This method offers a dependable and effective way to regularly check the quality of these substances in pharmaceutical products ⁽²⁰⁾.

Tanvi M. Bagul *et al.* (2022) created and verified a QbD-HPTLC method for estimating the levels of GUF, DXM, and CPM in combination pharmaceutical dosage forms. Mobile phase consist of methanol, ethyl acetate and ammonium and stationary phase was silica gel 60 F254 TLC plate. Detection with densitometry occurred at 254 nm. CPM's retention factor value was 0.22, DXM's 0.45, also GUF's 0.68. For all analytes, correlation coefficients (R^2) exceeded 0.998, and the method demonstrated outstanding linearity over concentration ranges of 100–600 ng regarding CPM, 200–1200 ng regarding DXM, and 500–3000 ng/spot regarding GUF. They assessed validation parameters so this assessment was following the ICH guidelines ⁽²¹⁾.

Lamia M *et al.* (2023) devised and verified HPTLC densitometry technique for measurement of AS, PA, DXM, CA, and CPM in over-the-counter pills. 25% ethyl acetate, methanol, and ammonia solution in a ratio of 8.5:1:0.5 (v/v/v) comprised the mobile phase and separation was accomplished on silica gel 60 F254 plates. All analytes showed crisp, symmetrical, and well-resolved peaks after detection at 254 nm. Vegaskin-D tablets were successfully analysed using the techniques, demonstrating their applicability in routine quality control for pharmaceutical formulations with several components ⁽²²⁾.

Adarsh Leuva *et al.* (2024) created and verified The HPTLC technique for determining DEX, PE, and CPM in pharma syrup formulations. Silica gel 60 F254 plates were used for the chromatographic procedure, which used a mobile phase consisting of 2.5:7.5:0.3 (v/v/v) chloroform, methanol, and ammonia. Detection wavelength was 270 nm. This combination allowed for the successful separation of the specified analytes. With correlation coefficients (R^2) continuously over 0.995, the new approach showed excellent linearity across the investigated ranges like 1000–3500 ng (PE), 3000–11500 ng (DEX) and 400–1400 ng (CPM) per bands. Furthermore, evaluations of precision and robustness showed RSD values less than 2%, demonstrating the method's dependability ⁽²³⁾.

Gas Chromatography

Fatang Yang *et al.* (2022) created a rapid and simultaneous GC-FID method to find several powerful ingredients in anticatarrhal agents. Both standard and sample were carefully weighed, diluted in ethanol, filtered and ultrasonically degassed, the gas chromatograph was used for detection. In 7.0 minutes, all six components were fully separated. The sensitivity, accuracy, precision, and recovery rate of this approach are all good. The LOQ was 1.20–8.30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, while the LOD was 0.360–2.50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ under ideal testing circumstances. Linearity was observed in the range of 1.20 to 400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and $R^2 \geq 0.9932$. The recoveries ranged between 89.2% and 109.2%. Precision was also within the limit. Results indicate, this method can accurately identify the constituents of three anti-cold medications that are already on the market. The technique can identify several active components in anti-cold medications quickly and concurrently. The advantages of the suggested approach include speed, ease of use and affordability. It offers a standard procedure for ensuring the active components in anti-cold medications are of high quality ⁽²⁴⁾.

Lamia M *et al.* (2023) developed a GC-FID method to concurrently measure the amounts of CA, AS, PA, CPM, and DXM in over-the-counter medications. Using a capillary column and nitrogen as the carrier gas, the method demonstrated the ability to effectively separate the analytes as well as salicylic acid, the primary consequence of aspirin breakdown. This approach is useful for stability investigations as well. The results showed how well the recommended methods worked for regular medication analysis and quality control in fixed-dose combo tablets ⁽²²⁾.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography

Fuad Al-Rimawi *et.al* (2010) proposed a simple, accurate, and exact method for analyzing DXM, PA, PSE and CPM in tablets. This process has effectively isolated the four components from one another. Methanol and phosphate buffer (90:10 v/v) in a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min eluted the components on a silica column and detected the analytes at 220 nm. This validated method exhibited a linearity range of 0.075 to 0.225 mg/ml of DXM ($R^2 = 0.992$), 0.01 to 0.03 mg/ml of CPM ($R^2 = 0.994$), 0.15 to 0.45 mg/ml of PSE ($R^2 = 0.996$), and 0.25 to 0.75 mg/ml of PA ($R^2 = 0.991$). This method was also discovered to be strong and resilient⁽²⁵⁾.

Shalini Joshi *et.al* (2012) proposed a method to estimate DXM and LCZ in antitussives using an isocratic RP-HPLC method. These chemicals were separated in 10 minutes on a C18 column using mobile phase of acetonitrile, tetrahydrofuran, and potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 2.5) in the ratio 70:25:5, v/v/v. Elution rate was 1.2 ml/min and detection at 232 nm. The accuracy and RSD were 100.36% and 0.05% for LCZ and 100.35% and 0.27% for DXM, respectively. By contrasting their peak areas with those of recently prepared standard solutions, the constituents in the syrup formulation were measured. The process was confirmed to comply with ICH guidelines⁽²⁶⁾.

Tarun Goyal *et.al* (2013) outlined an isocratic HPLC technique for the simultaneous measurement of CPM, DXM and GUF. On a Purospher star RP-18e column, the three drugs were separated chromatographically employing a mobile phase of 74% phosphate buffer and 26% acetonitrile. The UV detection process took 13 minutes to complete and was performed at 225 nm. The method was further validated. Each molecule was subjected to stress testing by treating with acid, alkali, hydrogen peroxide and UV light to show the procedure's specificity and the successful resolution of the degradation products generated⁽²⁷⁾.

Sakshi Sawant *et.al.* (2014) suggested an HPLC method to find GUF, DXM, PE and CPM in cough medicines. Acetonitrile and 0.05% ortho-phosphoric acid were utilized as the mobile phase on a C18 column. The elution rate was 1.0 mL/min. It was detected at 214 nm. The method was tested in accordance with ICH criteria and shown good linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness. However, this method's drawback is the potential for excipient effect in complex formulations⁽²⁸⁾.

Kapildev R Jaiswal *et al* (2016) presented a method for estimating the amounts of PE, CPM, and DXM in cough syrup using RP-HPLC. At 265 nm, the absorbance is measured. This method employs an isocratic mode of separation on a Partisil 10 SCX column at $35^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ using buffer and methanol (40:60% v/v) as mobile phase and an ambient flow rate. Complete separation was achieved within 13 minutes. The R^2 for all three analytes was 0.9999. The developed processes were validated to meet ICH requirements. The method was found to be linear within 5–15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 2.5–7.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 1-3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for PE, CPM, and DXM, respectively⁽²⁹⁾.

Vishal Jain *et.al* (2016) proposed an RP-HPLC method to determine GUF, CPM, DXM, and BRX in tablet dosage form. Methanol, acetonitrile, and 0.025 M phosphate buffer (50:25:25, v/v/v) eluted on a Chromatopak C18 column with maximum absorbance at 265 nm. The retention periods for BRX, CPM, DXM, and GUF were 16.254 minutes, 12.219 minutes,

6.156 minutes, and 9.432 minutes, respectively. All the validation parameters tested were aligned to the ICH standards⁽³⁰⁾.

S. Ashutosh Kumar *et al.* (2016) developed a gradient RP-HPLC technique to estimate the levels of DXM, CPM, and PE in syrups. The method uses UV detection at 220 nm. To achieve good chromatographic separation, an analytical stainless steel column called the Hypersil BDS C8 was utilized. The flow rate was maintained at 1.0 mL/minute and the system temperature was $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The mobile phase used was acetonitrile and a mixture of TEA and sodium salt of 1-octane sulfonic acid with a pH of 3.2. The mentioned techniques, linearity, specificity, accuracy, and precision, were all verified⁽³¹⁾.

Meruva Sathish Kumar *et al.* (2017) created a gradient RP-HPLC-PDA method to test CPM, DXM, PA, and PE simultaneously in commercial formulations and bulk. The best results were obtained when chromatography was performed using a C8 column with phosphate buffer and acetonitrile (70:30), eluted at 1 ml/m and detected at 225 nm. Separation of all analytes was achieved within 6 minutes. In compliance with ICH criteria, this method demonstrated good linearity, accuracy, and precision. Linearity ranges from 0.5 to 487.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. After a day, there was no noticeable change in the injected sample, which reveals stability. The range of recovery was 100.38 to 100.53⁽³²⁾.

Marija Zafirova *et al.* (2018) propose the HPLC/DAD method for estimating cough and cold active ingredients and their contaminants. Two preservatives, sodium benzoate and propyl parahydroxybenzoate, as well as eleven active components and five of their impurities, were isolated. The separation of all the component analytes was achieved with exceptional sensitivity and resolution in 14 minutes, utilizing a column with porous particles, superficial and gradient elution with a mobile phase made up of formic acid in water and acetonitrile. The design of experiments methodology was used to further optimise the strategy. The suggested approach enables the concurrent qualitative and quantitative determination of the chosen chemicals in various cough and cold dose forms and has been validated by ICH requirements⁽³³⁾.

Azza A. Moustafa *et al.* (2018) suggested using a sensitive HPLC method to detect IBU, PSE, and CPM in tablet form all at once. Methanol, acetonitrile, and distilled water (pH 4) in the ratio 80:10:10, v/v, were used as the mobile phase for RP-HPLC analysis on a Zorbax C8 column at a flow rate of 0.7 mL min⁻¹. UV detection at 220 nm was used to obtain quantification. The ICH guidelines were followed in the validation of the suggested procedures. The specified medications were successfully identified in commercial dosage form and bulk powder using the recommended methodology⁽³⁴⁾.

Najam ud Din *et al.* (2018) established and verified an accurate and sensitive RP-HPLC technique for simultaneously determining DXM and CPM in different matrices employing a photo-diode array detector. Using an isocratic elution mode, a methanol and phosphate buffer (60:40, v/v) mobile phase, a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min, and UV detection at 230 nm, the separation occurred on a C-18 column in 8 minutes. An external metric was used to measure the results. CPM was retained at 3.83 minutes and DXM at 5.02 minutes. This new method

shows good linearity between 1-200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with R^2 of 0.9994 (CPM) and 2-1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with R^2 of 0.9993 (DXM). Also, the detection and quantification limits were 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 1.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively, and 0.50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 1.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Consistency of the sample in the HPLC injector remained same for 12 hours, and matrix interference was not found. The developed method, which used a liquid/liquid extraction process, was shown to be accurate and had recovery rates for both analytes that ranged from 90.0% to 101.9%. Both within and between days, precision was less than 2.5 percent. The technique, which makes use of physiological and pharmaceutical matrices, was shown to be dependable and repeatable⁽³⁵⁾.

Chengalva Prasanthi *et al.* (2018) created and validated an RP-HPLC technique to estimate DXM and CPM in tablets. Water and acetonitrile (60:40v/v) were eluted on a C18 column at a flow rate of 1 ml/min to separate the analytes. Absorbance maxima were found to be 218 nm. Dextromethorphan and chlorpheniramine maleate were shown to have retention periods of 3.6 and 3.0 minutes, respectively. The suggested approach was verified as per ICH regulations⁽³⁶⁾.

Abdrhman Gamil *et al.* (2020) proposed an RP-HPLC method to assess DXM, GUF, PSE, and CPM simultaneously in pharmaceutical formulations. A 210 nm detector, a C₁₈ column, and a mobile phase made up of triethanolamine, phosphate buffer, acetonitrile, and orthophosphoric acid were used to design the procedure. The column oven operates at 400°C for 60 minutes at an average rate of 0.8 millilitres per minute. The validation parameters were all confirmed in accordance with the ICH guidelines. The stability of the solution, the detection limit, and the quantitation limit had all been evaluated. The compounds show retention at 50.44, 15.85, 12.63, and 5.5 minutes, respectively. It was found that the theoretical plates surpass 2000, the resolution between the peaks is above 20, the tailing factor is not larger than 2, and the RSD% is less than 1%. Sufficient linearity was indicated by the method's correlation coefficient (R^2), which ranged from 0.9996 to 0.9998. The test solution remains stable for 2 days. The method is easy, rapid, and meets all acceptable requirements for each validation parameter⁽³⁷⁾.

Seyyed Alireza M H *et al.* (2020) created a selective RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous measurement of DXM, CPM, and 10 other active substances along with methyl, ethyl, and butyl parabens as preservatives. Many cough and cold medications contain these active pharmacological components. An Atlantis d C18 column was employed for the separation. The eluent used was an ion-pairing buffer solution and acetonitrile at a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹. Acetonitrile was employed as an organic modifier on a gradient system. To quantify the active components at 290 and 215 nm, this approach used wavelength program detection. Validation was carried out in accordance with ICH requirements and was found to be helpful for routinely analysing over-the-counter medications that contain these active ingredients⁽³⁸⁾.

T. Yuliana *et al.* (2021) proposed and verified an HPLC method to detect DXM and CPM with potassium sorbate as preservative in cough syrup. Five distinct concentrations were made, with three separate runs for each concentration, and the determination was performed on a simulated sample made up of three components. The C18 column was used to achieve the ideal HPLC conditions, which included UV absorption at 230 nm. With the column

temperature set at 35 °C, the gradient elution method was used to pump acetonitrile & phosphate buffer pH 2.5, along with ion pairing agents, at a rate of 1 ml/min. With recovery between 98% to 102%, linearity ($r \geq 0.98$), and RSD < 2%, the results demonstrated that the strategy had satisfied the validation test requirements. The strategy was also shown to be selective. LOD and LOQ were also found to be within the limit⁽³⁹⁾.

Zeinab Adel Nasr *et al.* (2021) created a sustainable micellar HPLC method with a goal of ecological sustainability for detecting CPM, LCF, DXM and DEX in various matrices. Using a micellar aqueous mobile phase made up of sodium dodecyl sulphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate, and ethanol, the separation was performed on a Kinetex C18 column with UV detection at 230 nm. Using isocratic elution, the four medications were successfully separated in a single run lasting no more than seven minutes. Within the concentration ranges of 5–60 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for CPM, 10–100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for LCF and DXM, and 5–30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for DEX, the method exhibited linearity, accuracy, and precision in accordance with ICH recommendations. Additionally, the suggested method's environmental friendliness and minimal impact were assessed using two different techniques⁽⁴⁰⁾.

Adel Ehab Ibrahim *et al.* (2021) introduced a micellar liquid chromatography (MLC) approach for the simultaneous study of six anti-cold medications, including DXM and CPM. This approach used response surface techniques to forecast the conditions. The eluent consist of SDS and Brij-35 mixed with phosphate buffer at pH 5.2. Stationary phase was maintained at 35° C and absorbance maxima was set at 215 nm. Twelve distinct analyte blends in their pharmaceutical products were effectively identified by the approach, which was evaluated for greenness based on two new criteria. The Green Analytical Procedure Index and the Analytical Greenness Metric were used to evaluate the method, and a detailed comparison with methods that had already been published was given⁽⁴¹⁾.

Ali E. Karim *et al.* (2023) established and confirmed a novel HPLC technique to detect the levels of DXM, CPM, and PSE in syrups. The Chromegabond WR C18 column has been used for chromatographic separation. Sodium perchlorate mixture was used as the mobile phase. Eluent rate set at 1.5 ml/min. Absorbance maxima were 262 nm, and an injection volume of 20 μl . All analytes were effectively separated within the short time span. The recovery ranged from 98.0 to 102.0, the precision had an RSD of less than 2.0%, and the linearity of the approach was confirmed with high correlation coefficients. This method has been validated and applied successfully on marketed syrups from Iraq⁽⁴²⁾.

Vineetha Rosireddy *et al.* (2024) described an ecologically sound RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous detection of DXM, CPM, and PSE, as well as their degradant products. An Agilent column was used to achieve separation. Phosphate buffer and ethanol comprised the eluent at a rate of 1 mL/min. The injection volume was 10 μL , and the absorbance maxima of 220 nm. Gradient elution was used. Separating the three analytes took 12.2 minutes. The linear range of concentrations for CPM, PSE, and DXM was 2–12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 1-6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 1-6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. The corresponding correlation values were 0.999, 0.998, and 0.998. To further optimize the process, central composite design and green evaluation techniques were applied⁽⁴³⁾.

Ultra-performance liquid chromatography

A.J. Patel *et al.* (2020) proposed a stability-indicating RP-UPLC technique to measure the amounts of CPM and DXM in tablets. Acetonitrile (70:30% v/v) and trifluoroacetic acid in water were used as eluent at a rate of 0.2 mL/min, along with an RP-UPLC BEH C18 column as the stationary phase in this isocratic technique. Analytes were determined using PDA detection at 252 nm. The retention durations for CPM and DXM were 1.2 and 2.2 minutes, respectively. Acidic, photolytic, oxidative, alkaline, and thermal stress conditions were applied to the active substances. The technique was validated in accordance with ICH guidelines ⁽⁴⁴⁾.

Hyphenated techniques

Homeira Ebrahimzadeh *et al.* (2012) proposed a technique of hollow fibre liquid phase microextraction (HF-LPME) to evaluate DXM and CPM in human plasma. This technique was improved utilizing a response surface methodology and a four-variable study layout. The effects of time, salt addition, acceptor phase HCl concentration, and source phase pH were investigated. The analytes were separated in their neutralized state with a pH of 12.5 and a 2% (w/v) salt concentration into the HCl inside the hollow fibre lumen to be extracted again under ideal circumstances using a hexadecane membrane (SLM) The pH gradient fuelled the mass transit of the compounds across the donor to the acceptor phase ⁽⁴⁵⁾.

Hong-gang Lou *et al.* (2010) developed a LC-MS/MS technique for the simultaneous estimation of PAR, PE, DT, and CPM in human plasma. The Internal standard (IS) used was diphenhydramine. A C18 Column, a gradient program, and eluent made up of acetic acid and methanol at a rate of 0.30 mL/min were used to separate the analytes and IS. This method involves the use of a quadrupole spectrometer. Over a range of concentrations of 10-5000 ng/mL for PAR, 2-1000 ng/mL for PE, 0.05-25 ng/mL for DT, and 0.1-50 ng/mL for CPM, the approach was confirmed to be linear. All of the analytes had accuracy ranging from -8.37% to 3.13%, whereas the intra-day and inter-day precisions were lower than 11.54% and 14.35%, respectively. Additionally, this validated method was successfully conducted for the randomised crossover human trials ⁽⁴⁶⁾.

Ding *et al.* (2014) proposed an HPLC-MS/MS technique for determining DXM, DT, and CPM in human plasma. Initially, the analytes were separated from the plasma using ethyl acetate. This was followed by chromatographic separation using acetonitrile and a water-formic acid mixture as eluent at a flow rate of 0.2 mL/min. This was quantified using a triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometer. Between 0.01 and 5 ng/mL for DXM, 0.02 and 5 ng/mL for DT, and 0.025 and 20 ng/mL for CPM, the calibration curve was linear. The corresponding LOQs were 0.01 and 0.025 ng/mL. The accuracy was between 92.9 and 102.5 percent, and the precisions within and between days were within 11%. It was discovered that the analytes remained stable during the analytical and storage processes ⁽⁴⁷⁾.

Henedak *et al.* (2015) expanded the use of the hyphenated methodology by developing a UHPLC-MS/MS to detect DXM, TRD, CPM, and its metabolites in human plasma using ibuprofen as an internal standard. Analysis of the extracted samples from plasma was done using UHPLC combined with mass spectrometry. Chromatographic separation was achieved using the mobile phase, which consisted of acetonitrile, water, and formic acid (89.2:11.7:0.1), injected into a Hypersil-Gold C18 column at a flow rate of 0.25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The runtime was 2 minutes. In accordance with ICH principles, the procedure was further validated⁽⁴⁸⁾.

Capillary electrophoresis

Beytul Yener *et al.* (2022) optimised a capillary electrophoresis method for estimation of pseudoephedrine, chlorpheniramine, paracetamol, dextromethorphan, 4-aminophenol and ephedrine in tablets. Sodium borate buffer of pH 8.0 was used as electrolyte, separation voltage of 30 kV and 30°C capillary temperature. For 10 seconds, the injection pressure of the sample was kept at 50 mbar. The linearity of the calibration graphs was satisfactory. The RSD percentages for intraday and interday precision were less than 1.39% using the capillary electrophoresis method. Precision within and between days was below 1.39%. The devised method was shown to be quick and easy to use for determining the six analytes described above in tablet formulation, with recoveries ranging from 99.62 to 100.57% for each of the analytes⁽⁴⁹⁾.

CONCLUSION

The analytical techniques for determining dextromethorphan hydrobromide and chlorpheniramine maleate simultaneously have improved considerably, providing a range of approaches ideal for different pharmaceutical matrices. For routine analysis, spectrophotometric techniques are still straightforward and economical, but they are frequently constrained by spectral overlaps in intricate formulations. The ability to resolve multiple components and degradation products, as well as improved selectivity and precision, make chromatographic techniques such as HPLC and HPTLC suitable for stability studies and complex formulations. Although they come with higher operational costs and technical requirements, advanced hyphenated techniques such as UHPLC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS offer superior sensitivity and specificity, making them especially useful in pharmacokinetic and bioequivalence studies. To ensure dependable quality control and therapeutic safety, the formulation complexity, necessary sensitivity, regulatory requirements, and available resources should all be taken into consideration when choosing a method. This review can be used as a valuable reference for developing, optimizing and validating analytical procedures for DXM and CPM containing dosage forms.

ABBREVIATIONS

UV- Ultra violet, RP – Reverse phase, HPLC – High performance liquid chromatography , GC – Gas chromatography, TLC – Thin layer chromatography, HPTLC - High performance thin layer chromatography, LC-MS/MS – Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry/Mass Spectrometry, UHPLC- MS/MS – Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatography-Mass

Spectrometry/Mass Spectrometry, FID - Flame Ionization Detection, SARS CoV 2 - Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2, FDA - Food and Drug Administration, CNS – Central nervous system, CYP - Cytochrome P450, OTC - Over the counter , ODS – Octa decyl silane, LOD – Limit of detection , LOQ – Limit of quantitation, HCl- Hydrochloric acid, ICH – International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, RSD – Relative standard deviation, QbD – Quality by design, TEA – Triethylamine, PDA – Photodiode array, DAD – Diode array detector, SDS - Sodium dodecyl sulphate, SLM - supported liquid membrane

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